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THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING WORLD LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

Present article is devoted to the use of a computer in the process of teaching foreign language. The purpose of studying this discipline is named in it.

Keywords: teaching process, teaching methods, modern pedagogical technologies, information technology, computer.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching foreign languages in blended classes requires enormous effort on teachers' shoulders. As educators play the great role in this process. For this reason teachers always need to be in a move forward looking for new and interesting methods for teaching in order to motivate and increase students' knowledge and skills [1. 27].

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Thereupon, most educators trying to use ICT as it has more positive effects on teaching and learning process, as was mentioned in the article of Korkut Uluc Isisag "The positive effects of integrating ICT in 47 foreign language teaching" (international conference, ICT for language learning, 5th edition): 1. Adaptability of materials relying upon conditions and the necessities of learners'. 2. Permitting ICT to respond upon and empowering the use of recent and daily news, offering access to authentic materials on the web; 3. Possibility to join and to use basic skills (text and images, audio and video clip) 4. Providing lectures more fascinating and less conventional which lifts learners' engagement; 5. Empowering the ICT to concentrate on one particular part of the lesson (pronunciation, vocabulary).

As have been gaining experiences at lyceum where the students have being taught in several directions and depending on the direction the English classes are being provided (it can be accounted as an ESP).

However, disciples had been divided according to their future purposes and chosen sphere but there are still mixed leveled students can be noticed, as well as the levels and abilities of learners are mixed. Indeed there will be problems which are

having being noticed in multileveled classes for today. Naturally, they are connected with teaching and learning such groups.

The two monthly pedagogical practice showed that the new generation, who are being taught at educational institutions, like academic lyceums or colleges and schools are more interested in IT and ordinary teaching with only books or exercises are no more interesting and motivating them. Hence after observation, before starting the teaching practice had been chosen the mixed ability groups with some problems and prepared the materials according to the institution plans [2. 141].

During the practice, there was used ICT to overcome the problems which had been faced, like the effectiveness of learning, discipline, motivation and participation of students. For everyday teaching practice had been prepared additional handouts, topic based videos, songs, PPT presentations, except them the aspect course books also used. The influence of used materials was higher than it was expected¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In recent years, the question of the use of new information technologies in the learning process has been increasingly raised. These are not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process. If the goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of the communicative culture of students, teaching the practical mastery of a foreign language, then the teacher's task is to create conditions for the practical mastery of the language for each student and choose such teaching methods that would allow each student to show their activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages.

Modern pedagogical technologies such as collaborative learning, project-based methodology help to implement a student-centered approach to learning, provide individualization and differentiation of learning, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning, inclinations, etc. Everyone knows that until recently, teaching a foreign language was based on the traditional approach, which consists in informing the teacher of the amount of theoretical knowledge and developing students' abilities and skills in the discipline being studied.

In a classroom learning environment, the teacher does not always have the opportunity to pay due attention to each student, so many of them lose motivation to learn, which leads to a significant decrease in the level of their knowledge, skills and abilities. Therefore, one of the main tasks of a teacher is to activate the activity of each student in the learning process, to create a situation for their creative activity.

¹ Rakhimova F.Sh. Methods of using information technology in teaching foreign languages

The use of a computer helps to implement a student-centered approach to learning, provides individualization and differentiation, taking into account the characteristics of students, their level of knowledge. Currently, the role of the teacher in the educational process is changing. The nature of the teacher-student interaction is also changing qualitatively. Gradually, the main function of the teacher, as a source of knowledge, decreases. The modern task of the teacher is to direct the educational process in the right direction, provide links to quality resources and track the understanding of the material by the audience, help everyone in its development. Learning a foreign language using computer programs is of great interest to students. With the use of the latest developments in the field of teaching foreign languages based on the use of multimedia technology, the learning process has moved to a qualitatively different level. Based on this, we can say with confidence that even in conditions of artificial communication, it is possible to simulate situations of real, natural communication.

Several advantages of computer teaching of a foreign language should be highlighted: the creation of a favorable psychological climate, an increase in the motivation for learning a foreign language; technical advantages of teaching a foreign language using a computer: the ability to carry out technical translation; use grammar and spelling checkers; the use of multimedia, interactive video in teaching oral speech [1, p. 64].

CONCLUSION

The graphic capabilities of the computer distinguish this teaching method from the traditional one and allow the principle of visualization of teaching to be implemented. The educational value of computer networks, both local and global, is almost invaluable. Also, computer-assisted training makes it possible to organize the independent work of each student. Integration of a regular lesson with a computer allows the teacher to transfer part of his work to the computer, while making the learning process more interesting and intense. In this case, the computer does not replace the teacher, but only supplements him. The selection of training programs depends on the training material, the level of training of the trainees and their abilities. The forms of working with computer training programs in the classroom include the study of vocabulary, pronunciation practice, teaching dialogical and monologue speech, teaching writing, and practicing grammatical phenomena. The scope of application of the computer in teaching foreign languages is unusually wide, since the use of a computer provides students with the opportunity to work in an interactive field of study.

Overall, taking all facts mentioned above can make conclusion that the use of ICT is one of the effective ways to awake the learners and making the teachers to move forward, but not backward and its influence on teaching and learning process is huge but that covers not only positive sights but also negative sights as well. Thereupon, in teaching every strategy and methods are effective but there should be the middle limit of them.

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